

Comparing News in Print and Broadcast Media: An Exploratory Digital Analysis of Swiss Press and Radio

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Introduction

How does the medium influence the type of information presented? Does radio, constrained by its audio format, with programming schedules that leave little room for news and often limited by rules designed to prevent it from competing with print newspapers, present different information to its listeners than the press? And if there is a difference, is it primarily a purely quantitative one—with topics covered in greater detail in the media that has more space or airtime—or is it a different selection/prioritization of topics?

The aim of this paper is to lay the groundwork for a systematic and quantitative study of the news content of the press and radio in French-speaking Switzerland during the 20th century. While these media and their respective information policies have already been studied in their own right (Drack 2000, Clavier 2017), the challenge is to take advantage of recent digitization campaigns to ask these questions afresh, based on the archives themselves and explore the possibilities of digital media history (Balbi 2011, Michael and Werner 2024). This approach will highlight both the potential and the limitations of digital methods applied to these press and radio contents, and will enable discussion of the potential for comparison between very comprehensive press collections and radio archives, which are inevitably incomplete.

The physical space allocated to information: airtime and newspaper surface area

In French-speaking Switzerland, the place of news on the radio is heavily influenced by the fact that public service radio stations belonging to *Radio Suisse Romande* (RSR, which had a monopoly for decades, now called RTS since it merged with television) are strictly dependent on news bulletins from the Swiss Telegraphic Agency (ATS) for a long time. This is to prevent public radio from competing with private newspaper publishers. But beyond this short, regular news bulletin, RSR also devotes part of its airtime to current affairs programs.

In the same way that journalistic news content is buried among a mass of other types of articles in a newspaper, is it possible to reconstruct the evolution of the place of news on the radio? Following the example of Aubry et al. (2005, 40–56) and MacLennan (2005) we sample the magazine *Le Radio* (later *Radio TV Je vois tout*) to reconstruct the radio schedules of French-speaking Switzerland between 1920-1980 in order to assess the overall proportion of news content, which we then compare to a similar sample from two newspapers in the same region, digitized on the Impresso platform (Ehrmann 2021). This enables us to discuss the conditions for such sampling, the challenges of classifying the types of content broadcast on the radio and featured in newspaper columns, and to initiate a reflection on the cross-media comparability of these results.

The physical footprint of information in the newspaper

1 June 1950
Feuille d'Avis de Neuchâtel

An information paper that features classified ads prominently, along with news.

1 June 1950
Journal de Genève

A conservative newspaper that devotes a great deal of space to opinion pieces and news.

Even with sources as well-researched as newspapers, it is difficult to reach a consensus on **what constitutes a news article and what does not**. Furthermore, the definition evolves over time (and searching for «information» in the contemporary sense doesn't necessarily make sense in the context of the 19th century). The simplest approach is to use a process of elimination, removing anything that is clearly something else (advertisements, official announcements, classified ads).

The temporal footprint of radio news

RSR1 Total airtime (minutes in an average day)

RSR1 airtime distribution

It should be noted that between 1930 and 1970, the “gaps” in the schedule were often partially filled by simultaneous broadcasts from another Swiss channel.

1930 - The radio broadcast an **ATS news bulletin** late in the evening (5 minutes per day) and included a few **news programs** (13 minutes per day on average).

1940 - There are now **four ATS news bulletins**, each lasting nearly 10 minutes, read from Bern, in addition to about 20 minutes of **programs commenting on current events** every day.

1950 - **ATS news bulletins** have become shorter in the morning and late at night; they are now consistently framed by **in-house news reports or commentary programs**.

1960 - Situation was quite similar to that of the previous decade: news coverage (ATS bulletins and news programs) took about 1h30 per day. In 1966, the ATS bulletins were now read in Lausanne.

1970 - The bulletins are no longer produced by ATS but “in collaboration with” ATS. The schedule has been significantly revised: 5-minute news flashes every hour and three big blocks (“Journal”).

1980 - The structure remains the same, but the bulletins (“information gathered with the assistance of ATS”) are now longer and accompanied by a “news magazine.” News accounts for 25% of airtime.

1990 - There is no longer any mention of bulletins or ATS; everything is now grouped under the term "journal," which includes **topical sections** in addition to the **news**.

What archives do we actually have?

- RTS began digitizing its RSR archives in 1990 because the physical media were deteriorating. It was at that time that the heritage value of these collections was recognized.
- Before that, everything that was preserved was kept because it was thought it might be reused in other programs.
- The systematic recording of all programming began in the mid-2010s.

Average number of items per year held in the archives of the French-speaking Swiss radio station RSR1 (by decade)

Let's take the example of two weeks used as a reference before, in 1950 and 1980:

42 éléments trouvés pour *** du 11 juin 1950 au 15 juin 1950

Archived: 0 minutes of **ATS bulletins**, 38 minutes of **news programs** and 230 minutes of other contents

6% is archived

30 éléments trouvés pour *** du 14 juin 1980 au 20 juin 1980

Archived: 30 minutes of «**journal**», 26 minutes of **news programs** and 619 minutes of other contents

9% is archived

Limitations: Contains duplicates, entries with no associated records, and content that cannot be linked to specific programs.

Reality check: the limits of comparison

A week of RSR1 in the 1980s

7x 18 hours = 126 hours of airtime

25% is information
(bulletins and news magazines)

≅ 30 hours of information

5-10% is archived
but there's a conservation bias
against information because it's
unlikely to be reusable,
so more like 1-3%

≅ 1 hour of
radio information
available / week

From the typescripts, we know they
speak 120-150 words per minute
≅ 230 000 words equivalent if no
music, sounds, etc.

≅ 8 000 words

A week of a newspaper in the 1980s

5x or 6x 160 articles = 1000 articles

33-66% is information

≅ 500 articles

100% is archived
with a few exceptions

an article is 300-400 words

≅ 500 articles available / week

≅ 175 000 words

There is a factor 20 between press and radio archives

Analyzing the content of spoken news and the press: what overlaps?

While our first approach shows the context and density of information in the press and on the radio, this second part seeks to question the actual content of media coverage of news events. The aim is therefore to create a corpus of radio news recordings and newspaper articles covering the same geographical area and period in order to see how similar the topics covered are and whether either medium makes a particular selection. We therefore take the ATS typescripts and embed them with the corresponding press articles. The resulting semantic proximity map (Michelet and Grandjean 2026) allows us to document the correspondences but also, and above all, the differences, and to discuss the effect of the incompleteness of the radio archives on potential more systematic and larger historical press/radio studies.

Do the ATS typescripts cover the same news as the Journal de Genève?

The evening news ATS bulletin (radio) for Sunday, June 4, 1950, announcing election results that the press would not be able to report until the following day.

The goal is to understand the overlap between the two sources: a semantic categorization of news stories should make it possible to see whether the press and radio are covering the same events. If there is a difference, is it primarily a purely quantitative one – with topics covered in greater detail in the media that has more space or airtime – or is it a different selection/prioritization of topics?

The ATS radio typescripts are not as easy to analyze as newspaper articles because they have not been digitized.

For the purposes of this study, we followed the following protocol:

- Manual transcription of a small corpus in French and German to confirm that they contain the same information.
- Sampling: the entire month of June in 1940, 1945, 1950, 1955, 1960, and 1965.
- Photography of the 2,877 relevant pages at the Swiss National Library.
- OCR and correction of the transcription using an LLM (Claude, Sonnet 4.6), after verifying its reliability.
- Text segmentation using an LLM (Claude, Sonnet 4.6) to separate each news items.
- Text embeddings of these corpora, using the same model as the Impresso press articles, to enable accurate comparisons.

First statistical observation (see below): The size of ATS radio typescripts is extremely stable, both in terms of their overall length and the number of news items they contain.

June 1940		June 1945		June 1950		June 1955		June 1960		June 1965	
1350	1273	1438	1543	1378	970	1908	1052	1931	1048	2088	1197
JDG articles	ATS news										
442K	102K	544K	109K	640K	69K	767K	77K	785K	76K	962K	97K
words	words										
average	average										
327	80	378	70	464	71	401	73	406	72	460	81
words	words										

A semantic map of press articles and radio transcripts

June 1950 - 1378 JDG articles, 970 ATS news. Each dot represents a news item (size = word count).

Following this initial example, replication with each combined dataset every 5 years to assess the overlaps between newspaper articles and radio typescripts using UMAPs.

June 1940

The **Journal de Genève** is very interested in the situation in France which is on the verge of surrender, while the **ATS** reports much more news from the USSR, Italy, and United Kingdom.

June 1945

The situation is fairly balanced: **ATS** covers humanitarian issues (repatriation of prisoners, news from the Red Cross), while **Journal de Genève** has little specific national news coverage.

June 1950

Both cover the Korean War, but the **ATS** places greater emphasis on the Eastern Bloc, while the **Journal de Genève** focuses on economic negotiations in Europe.

June 1955

ATS provides much more coverage of the attempted coup in Argentina, while **Journal de Genève** focuses more on news from the emerging European community.

June 1960

The situation is fairly balanced, though the **ATS** still provides slightly better coverage of the Soviet Bloc than **Journal de Genève**.

June 1965

ATS is better at covering the Vietnam War than **Journal de Genève** and covers the floods in Switzerland and Europe (Danube) extensively.

Conclusion

There is indeed a factor of 10 in pure "surface area", in number of words between the radio ATS typescripts and a daily newspaper like *Journal de Genève*, but they are equal in number of subjects: radio covers as many, or even more, subjects than the press (if we count news programs and not just bulletins), but in most cases in a very short way (and we do not have access to long content, in-depth programs).

The challenge, for a good comparison, would be to **integrate long news programs** into this "big picture" (represented by the large question marks in the image above) or to **remove press articles that are not hard news** (represented by the large crosses above). And then to test the comparison with different newspapers: here we had a city newspaper with international ambitions. A more local newspaper will logically have less overlap with a national radio station.

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